

Facets Of Motivation, Attitude, And Non-Physical Fatigue With Work Productivity In Colleges

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Abstract

This study aims to describe the facets of motivation, attitudes, and non-physical fatigue with work productivity in tertiary institutions. This research uses the content analysis method. Content analysis is a technique that researchers can use to indirectly study human behavior through analysis of their communication such as textbooks, essays, newspapers, novels, magazine articles, songs, advertising images, and all types of communication that can be analyzed. From the studies that have been done, it can be concluded: First, motivation factors significantly affect job satisfaction. Employees will be motivated due to several factors, including an exciting and challenging job, an atmosphere that gives trust (trust), makes them personally responsible for the results, and is involved in the organization's growth and development. Second, attitude is a statement or evaluative consideration regarding objects, people, or events, and work attitudes can affect lecturers' performance in higher education. Third, stressors can harm the body. If this happens, there will be permanent damage to the body, resulting in non-physical fatigue. Fourth, lecturer work productivity is the achievement of all the lecturer's potential by utilizing the resources they have about time, quantity, and quality in carrying out their duties carrying out the tri dharma of higher education.

Introduction

Entering a new era in the 21st century, the higher education system in Indonesia must be realized in such a way with the following characteristics: (1) related to student needs, national priorities, and economic development, (2) structured effectively to provide opportunities for all citizens to develop their potential personal for life and contribute to society, nation and state, (3) supported by adequate funding to enable innovation and to achieve excellence, (4) conduct research that can support national development, (5) have access to technology development and application, and (6) play a role as a moral force in realizing a civilized democratic society (Bao, 2020; Toquero, 2020). Thus, universities must have complete and comprehensive institutional credibility. This system must have high accountability to the community, demonstrate efficiency in its operations, produce quality graduates, have transparent internal management, and meet standards

Human resources are an essential factor for organizations (Fleming, Maycock, White, & Depledge, 2019; Sinclair et al., 2019; Aslam, 2020). If human resources' performance is higher, it will increase efficiency, effectiveness, or high quality to complete each of the tasks assigned to the organization's work (Dessler, 2015). The role of human resources in determining the success of a company cannot be ignored. According to Smith, et.al. (2016), human resources are a competitive advantage that can face various challenges. This is also supported by Moscatto, et.al. (2013), which state that human resources play an essential role and determine a company's success.

To improve the framework for revitalizing an organization or company's strategy, human resources are one of the most strategic and fundamental factors in the organization. Compared to other factors, human resources are the most significant and valuable assets essential for the healthy operation of all other resources of the organization. So, when human resources are satisfied in terms of their work, all productivity levels will increase (Maimako & Bambale, 2016). Therefore, in supporting the use of human resources to create a competitive advantage, every employee must have the skills or skills to handle every job.

Fatigue at work is part of a common problem that is often encountered in the workforce. According to some researchers, fatigue can significantly affect workforce health and can reduce Productivity. So Productivity is a mental attitude that has the principle that today must be better than yesterday and tomorrow must be better than today. Every company always has the intention that its workforce can increase high Productivity. To achieve high Productivity, company leaders must pay attention to workplace morale and work discipline. Several factors, namely influence work productivity, both those related to the workforce itself and those related to other factors such as age, temperament, individual physical condition, fatigue, work motivation, physical

conditions such as sound, lighting, rest time, length of work, wages, the form of organization, social environment, and family (Mulyadi, et.al., 2020). According to Cascio, et.al. (2020), work productivity is Productivity as a measurement of output in the form of goods or services concerning inputs in the form of employees, capital, materials, or raw materials and equipment.

If someone cannot overcome the stressor, then the body will respond psychologically and impact someone's physical. Human labor requires special maintenance and development because other production factors will mean nothing without human work. For this reason, there is a need for occupational health efforts, namely protecting workers so that they live healthily and are free from health problems and harmful effects that result following the Law RI Law No. 36 of 2009 concerning Health. (RI, 2009)

One of the symptoms of workforce health problems that arise from work is fatigue. Fatigue from work is a problem that is often found in the workforce. Fatigue at work is a significant problem that needs to be adequately addressed because it can cause various issues such as loss of efficiency at work, decreased productivity and work capacity, and the ability to Health and the ability to survive the body causes work accidents. Fatigue is also a significant cause of work accidents and will affect productivity (Verawaty, et.al., 2017).

Various explanations regarding work productivity in development, such as the Human Development Index (HDI), have yet to show encouraging indicators. This clarifies the national labor productivity indicator in Indonesia that the productivity condition is inferior. Therefore, efforts to increase work productivity cannot be negotiated so that the national productivity ranking in Indonesia can be placed in a better position than in previous years (Rejeki, ., & Subandowo, 2019).

This relationship between productivity and health has been stated Fishbein & Ajzen (2005). It is also noted that the primary key or source of poverty is low worker productivity, intertwined with the causes of malnutrition, poor health, soft skills, low income, low savings, low investment, and low productivity (Pasaribu, et.al., 2015). From several studies on human resources, the role of investment in human resources significantly influences productivity (Kartasasmita & Stern, 2015). It is also stated that this increase in labor productivity can be encouraged through education and training and an increase in the degree of health in studies on productivity factors.

Concerning these research questions, this study aims to see the relationship between the facets of motivation, attitudes, and non-physical fatigue with work productivity. This research also examines the characteristics of teaching staff and education in tertiary institutions from work productivity in universities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Studies that have been conducted by Steers, et.al., (2005) and (Hidayat & Siagian (2017) show that motivation is a fundamental factor and affects a person's performance in carrying out his duties. Meanwhile, the studies that have been conducted by Alhassan & Nketiah-Amponsah (2016), Dessler (2016), and Laure Sellier & Darren (2015) also classify three motives, namely achievement motive, affiliation motive, and power motive into social motivation. Another study conducted by (McClelland, 1985) classified cause that influences humans into social reasons theory. This theory includes: (1) The need for achievement or need for achievement (nach) is the need to succeed by demonstrating higher mastery abilities, (2) The need for affiliation or need for collaboration (naff), which is the need for love and togetherness or belonging, the need to have friends from various backgrounds, and is accepted by Ling. high social environment, (3) The need for power or lack of energy (nop), which is the need to master one's work or control other people at work, the need to rule, the need for autonomy, and the need for independence and freedom.

Several research studies have proven that the positive influence or impact of the work environment on motivation and job performance (Andrews, 2009; Vischer, 2007; Vischer, 2008; Vimalanathan, 2013; Samson & Waiganjo, 2015). First, increasing human resources' work productivity creates the right work environment (Chavez et.al., 2015). Various research studies have discussed the impact of environmental work on motivation and job performance on different industrial sectors, such as tourism and hospitality (Pawirosumarto, et.al, 2017; Jayaweera, 2015), creative industries (Chavez, et.al, 2015), industry mining (Mensah & Tawiah, 2015), the education sector (Khan, et.al, 2011; Ali & Bahron, 2013) and the financial industry sector (Samson & Waiganjo, 2015).

Motivation is an impulse that causes a person to do an action to achieve a specific goal. Motivation comes from the word motive, which means "impulse" or stimulation or "driving force" in a person. Robbins (2010) states that motivation is the process that counts for an individual's intensity, direction, and persistence of effort toward attaining a goal. Based on this understanding, motivation can be defined as influencing other people to behave regularly. From the definition of motivation above, it can be seen that there are three things, which include efforts, organizational goals, and needs. The effort element is a measure of intensity. If someone is motivated, he will try to repeat the previous action. However, it is unlikely that a high level of effort will lead to performance and pay off. If that effort is channeled in a direction that is beneficial to the organization, it will achieve the organization's goals. From the above presentation, it can be seen that motivation can come from

within a person in the form of awareness of the importance of the benefits of their work. Motivation has three elements that are most related to one another, consisting of needs, drives, and goals. Meanwhile, Weinhrice & Koontz (1993) stated that motivation is a term that is generally used for all forms of wants, needs, and feelings of security.

According to Robbins & Judge (2008), as an evaluative statement, both pleasant and unpleasant towards objects, individuals, or events. This reflects how a person feels about a. According to Kotler & Armstrong (2010), attitude is an evaluation of an individual's feelings and tendencies towards a relatively consistent object. Attitude puts people in a frame of mind about liking or disliking something, about, approaching, or away from it. According to Muchlas (2005), attitude is involved, which can be defined as evaluative statements, both pleasant and unpleasant, or judgments about objects, people, or events.

Work fatigue is a condition experienced by workers that can decrease work vitality and productivity. In this study, work fatigue is general fatigue experienced by workers, characterized by a slowdown in reaction time and feelings of fatigue (Suma'mur, 2009). The brain centrally regulates fatigue. In the central nervous system, there are activation (sympathetic) and inhibition (parasympathetic) systems. The term fatigue usually indicates different conditions for each individual, but they lead to a loss of efficiency and a decrease in the body's endurance work capacity. The effects of the conditions that cause fatigue are like gathering in the body, resulting in fatigue feelings. Such high levels of fatigue can cause a person to no longer work to stop working, as is the case with physiological fatigue, which results in physical laborers who work physically stopping their activities because they feel tired and even sleep due to fatigue. Suma'mur (2009) states that fatigue is a variety of conditions accompanied by decreased efficiency and endurance at work, which can be caused by (a) fatigue whose primary source is the eyes, (b) general physical fatigue, (c) nervous exhaustion, (d)) fatigue by a monotonous environment, (e) chronic environmental fatigue as a constant factor. Fatigue shows different conditions for each individual, but all of them lead to a loss of efficiency and decreased work capacity and endurance (Tarwaka, 2008). A worker will feel tired if he has worked for 6 hours to 8 hours.

Meanwhile, non-physical mistakes can be said to be false fatigue, which arises in the feelings of a person concerned and is seen in his behavior or opinions that are no longer consistent. His soul is unstable with changes even in environmental conditions or his condition. So this concerns modifications related to a person's morale because this fatigue can be caused by several things, including lack of interest in work, various diseases, environmental conditions, the existence of binding moral laws and feeling inappropriate, mental causes such as responsibility, worry, and conflict. This influence seems to accumulate in the body and causes fatigue.

In line with the above view, Sedarmayanti (2001) states that work productivity shows that the individual is a comparison of the effectiveness of output (achievement of maximum performance) with the efficiency of one input (labor), which includes quantity and quality within a particular time. Work productivity is a measure of a person's work or performance with the input process as input and output as an output, which is an indicator of employee performance in determining how to achieve high productivity in an organization. In this research, what is meant by work productivity is a performance appraisal or performance appraisal, which is a systematic depiction of an individual or group related to the strengths and weaknesses of a job as a form of evaluation for individuals relating to the implementation of their organization (Cascio, 1998).

As the motor of productivity rather than this is human resources. Human resources as agents of change in the development process require skills and knowledge to develop high productivity. Employees who are part of the organization or company need to increase their productivity from the company's feedback to maintain and bind the employees to keep joining the company. Job satisfaction for an employee will positively impact the company, which of course, increases productivity for the company. Individuals as employees need good attention in their work.

METHOD

Qualitative research is influenced by the naturalistic-interpretive paradigm (Cresswell, Plano-Clark, Gutmann, & Hanson, 2003). The researcher tries to construct reality and understand its meaning to pay close attention to processes, events, and authenticity. This research uses the content analysis method. Fraenkel & Wallen (2006) states that content analysis is a technique that researchers can use to indirectly study human behavior by analyzing their communication, such as textbooks, essays, newspapers, novels, magazine articles, songs, and advertising images, and all types of communication. It can be analyzed.

Guba & Lincoln (2008) suggest five basic content analysis principles: (1) the process of following the rules. Each step is carried out based on rules and procedures arranged explicitly, (2) content analysis is a systematic process. This means that in the context of category formation, the entry and exclusion of categories are carried out based on rules that comply with principles, (3) content analysis is a process directed to generalize, (4) content analysis questions the manifested content. So if the researcher is going to conclude, it must be based on the contents of a manifested, (5) content analysis can be analyzed quantitatively. Still, it can also be done by qualitative research.

The steps or content analysis procedures are also described by Fraenkel & Wallen (2006) as follows: (1) the researcher decides the specific goals to be achieved, (2) defines important terms that must be explained in detail, (3) specifies units to be analyzed, (4) looking for relevant data, (5) building rational or conceptual relationships to explain how the data relates to objectives, (6) planning sampling, (7) formulating category coding. After the researcher has found as much detail as possible about the content's aspects to be studied, he needs to develop the relevant categories.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

1. The motivational facet

Based on Prabu et al. (2006) research results, motivational factors significantly affect employee job satisfaction. This shows that the higher the motivational factors given, the higher the employee job satisfaction. One of the motivating employee factors, namely the existence of trust by providing employees the opportunity to know everything in the company, will form an atmosphere of mutual trust and a strong work team. If employees are not informed about their progress, they feel mistrusted and less motivated to work.

According to Farida, Iqbal & Kurniasih (2016), job satisfaction is an essential issue in improving personal, organizational, and community life. When employees are satisfied, they will provide optimal work results and give individual, household, and community life happiness. In contrast, high dissatisfaction will result in high turnover and absenteeism rates at work, and life feels unhappy and less motivated to do something positive and productive. The employee job satisfaction factor is crucial for the company because of the satisfaction of employees. It is hoped that later it will further improve performance and have an impact on increasing the overall productivity of the company, or in-service management science known as "happy employee, happy customer," which means before satisfying customers, must first give satisfaction to workers, so that workers will be happy and sincere to provide optimal service for their customers (Muayyad & Gawi, 2017). Job satisfaction is an individual thing, and each individual has a different level of job satisfaction according to his wishes and the value system he adopts (Handoko, 2011).

Meanwhile, social motivation itself, according to McClelland & Burnham, (2017); (Heim, 2020) and Sanders et al. (1976), are classified into three motives, namely achievement motives, affiliation, and power motives into social motivation. David McClelland further classifies motivation that affects human needs, known as social motives theory, including a) The need for achievement (need for achievement, *nach*) is the need for success, to demonstrate a higher mastery ability; b) The need for affiliation (need for affiliation; *naff*) is the need for love togetherness (belonging), and association; the need to have friends from circles and be accepted in a high social environment; c) the need for power (need of power, *pow*) is the need to master one's work or to control other people at work, the need to govern, the need for autonomy, the need for independence and freedom. When the social motivation facet is seen from its indicators, It is very in line with the teacher's competency function profile. This social motivation is a response to stimulation. The resulting cognitive in social motivation will become a fundamental factor that affects a person's performance in carrying out his duties (M. Subandowo, 2009). In the case example in the field of work, which is analogous to teacher performance based on the study results, it is revealed that interesting tasks are precisely what affects job performance, not the size of the wages for doing them.

Other studies showing that motivation affects productivity are stated by Anita (2017); Laksmiari, (2019); Baiti et al. (2020), which in their research concluded that motivation has a positive and significant effect on work productivity. It is further argued that providing motivation both internally and externally will increase employee productivity.

Based on the above discussion, it can be synthesized that motivation factors significantly affect job satisfaction. In general, employees will be motivated because of several factors. One of them is an exciting and challenging job, an atmosphere that gives trust (trust), making them personally responsible for the results and being involved in the organization's growth and development.

2. Attitude

Work Attitude is something that is important and becomes a part of human life. In work, an individual reflects his attitude in a robust, complex, and varied manner. Furnham (2012) states that social values and beliefs shape work attitudes. These values put forward freedom, equality, love, and sacrifice, which are considered positively related and relevant in the workplace—matters associated with a group's belief system for particular objects and processes.

Suherman (2017) states that an attitude is a statement or evaluative consideration about an object, person, or event. When connecting the behavioral components of an attitude, it can be interpreted as an intention to behave in a certain way towards someone or something. When someone speaks showing a work attitude, it forms three things: job satisfaction, job involvement, and commitment to the organization. When an employee is at the point of acceptance for the organization's values, they will feel job satisfaction, involve themselves in work involvement, and give the commitment to the organization.

The work involvement of an individual in the organization will show and show the extent and how much involved in the work, feel the drift in position (flow), find enjoyment in sweat as if not limited to space and time, unite between work and competence, and perceive the importance of the job, for his actualization and self-worth.

Individuals' work involvement to state their actualization and self-esteem will be the basis that forms an individual to maintain the existence and partisanship of work and in the organization, or it can be stated that the individual is already committed to the organization. Such conditions will lead individuals to believe that their organization is a place to make a living, not just like a second home, which provides a sense of comfort, but an organization that is a place to organize the future. Such conditions will encourage individuals to intrinsically have the drive (motivation) to do their best as their capacity and capability professionally to carry out their functions, roles, and duties to produce the performance that focuses on quality.

For this reason, the transformation of the cultural values of work attitudes is fundamental in shaping the academic atmosphere in higher education so that quality becomes an attainable goal achievement.

The research was conducted by Sembiring (2018) to find out how the influence of work attitudes and work motivation on lecturer performance shows the results of the study that works attitude and work motivation can significantly influence the improvement of lecturer performance and work attitudes and work motivation jointly affect lecturer performance and significant.

The relationship between attitude and work productivity was also stated by several researchers, including (Pitriyani, Abd. Halim, 2019), who argued that work attitudes, work skills affect work productivity. Work attitudes significantly affect work productivity (Lewis, 2014, Amodu et al., 2017).

Based on the above discussion, it can be synthesized that attitude is a statement or evaluative consideration regarding objects, people, or events, and work attitudes can affect lecturers' performance in higher education.

3. Non-Physical Fatigue

Fatigue at work is part of a common problem that is often encountered in the workforce. According to some researchers, fatigue can significantly affect workforce health and reduce productivity (Atiqoh, Wahyuni, & Lestantyo, 2014). Fatigue is a common thing in human life as a result of doing an activity. Fatigue can be in the form of muscle fatigue, fatigue due to stress or depression, or fatigue due to certain diseases (Harring, Rohlf, & Palentien, 2007). Factors that affect fatigue include the type of activity, duration of the activity, workload, physical condition, physiological conditions, and psychological conditions. However, the relationship between stress and fatigue is not known with certainty because related research is still limited.

If someone cannot overcome the current stressor, the body will respond psychologically and impact one's physicality (Lumban Gaol, 2016). When under pressure, there will be a psychophysiological process in which the stressor will be processed through the mental level first, then physiologically. Physiological processes due to stress involve three systems, namely: (1) the central and peripheral nervous systems, (2) the endocrine system, and (3) the immune system, which interact with and secrete hormones that change the physiological homeostasis of the body. Each hormone can cause direct, moderate, or prolonged effects that cause the body to be ready to carry out the "Fight or Flight" mechanism (Rosanti, Dan, Budiastuti, Kunci, & Kebisingan, 2014). Meanwhile, according to Selye, when faced with prolonged stress, the body responds through three phases, namely; (1) Alarm Reaction, which resembles a fight or flight response, (2) Resistant Phase, which is when the body tries to compensate for existing stress, and (3) Exhaustion Phase, which is when the body is no longer able to pay for stressors due to exhaustion. It is in this phase that burnout and chronic fatigue syndrome occur (Smit BN, 2015).

Research conducted by Setyowati (2014) states that fatigue is directly affected by work stress, work conflicts, the physical environment, and work capacity. Budiono (2008) says that fatigue is characterized by a weakening of the workforce in doing work or activities to increase errors in doing work and its fatal consequences, namely the occurrence of work accidents.

Lazarus carried out various models that describe the mechanisms of stress and fatigue in 1966, Walter Cannon (1914) in the Fight or Flight response model, Hans Selye (1984) in the General Adaptation Syndrome (GAS) model, and the physiological interactions of the nervous, endocrine, and nervous systems. And the immune system as described by Seaward (2015). However, Hans Selye's GAS concept can explain in this study how stress is related to fatigue. GAS has three phases, starting with the Alarm Reaction, which is the body's response to being first exposed to a stressor, where this phase resembles Cannon's Fight or Flight response. The changes that occur in the body as an initial response to stressors do not last forever. If exposure to stressors continues, energy will decrease, and the body will stop resisting. This phase is called the resistance phase (Seaward, 2015).

Prolonged exposure to stressors can harm the body because a person's energy is limited and can be deleted at any time. If this happens, there will be permanent damage to the body. The organism's energy will

continue to be depleted due to continuous resistance until it can cause death (Romas & Sharma, 2017; Prasanty, Husada, Effendy & Simbolon, 2018).

To date, few studies have been conducted to examine the factors that influence the relationship between stress and fatigue and the specific mechanisms by which stress affects fatigue in more depth. Therefore, further research is needed regarding the causal relationship of stress with fatigue, the factors that influence it, and the specific mechanisms of how stress and fatigue are related. The results showed that there was a significant relationship between stress and fatigue (Natanhia, 2000). Meanwhile, Verawaty's (2016) study shows no relationship between working tenure and subjective fatigue. There is no relationship between nutritional status and emotional exhaustion. There is a relationship between subjective fatigue and productivity.

Fatigue at work is a variety of conditions accompanied by decreased efficiency and resilience at work (Suma'mur, 2009). Exhaustion from work will reduce performance and increase the level of work errors (Nurmianto, 2003). Fatigue at work is one factor that decreases performance, which can increase the error rate in work (Nurmianto, 1996). Besides, fatigue will significantly affect the results of the work that will be obtained or productivity. This is under the research results conducted by Anwar in Junaidi (2003), who saw the relationship between education and job training with employee work productivity in the ceramic company Soekardi Malang. The results of his research indicate that there is a significant and robust relationship between education and job training and employee productivity.

Based on the above discussion, it can be synthesized that stressors can harm the body because a person's energy is limited and can run out at any time. If this happens, there will be permanent damage to the body. Non-physical fatigue is the result of work stress, work conflicts, the physical environment, and work capacity. There is a relationship between stress and non-physical fatigue.

4. Work Productivity

Lecturer work productivity is closely related to lecturers' duties and functions in carrying out the tri dharma of higher education. Muchdarsyah (2000) defines productivity as an interdisciplinary approach to determining practical goals, making plans, using productive methods to use resources efficiently, and maintaining high quality.

Increasing work productivity is only possible by humans. Conversely, humans can also be the cause of waste and inefficiency in various forms. Human factors greatly influence work productivity, such as sleep problems, biological needs, and work fatigue. It is even argued that the decrease in labor productivity in the field is mostly due to work fatigue. Therefore, paying attention to the human element is one of the demands in the overall effort to increase work productivity.

Work productivity is the ability to produce something that emphasizes quality output by utilizing existing inputs effectively and efficiently. As stated by Lubis (2012), Eviyan Ihsani et al. (2017), Engkoswara & Komariah (2010), Lubis (2012), Suwena (2008) defines work productivity as the result of the ability to utilize resources to complete work tasks related to the quality of work results, quantity of work results, work effectiveness, and work efficiency, measured by comparing the results achieved and the resources used.

Hartatik (2014) states that work productivity indicators are as follows: 1. Results of yields. It has been explained previously that productivity is a person's ability to produce goods and services. Based on this opinion, with the presence of low employee work productivity, the production of goods or services will automatically decrease, so that the production target is not achieved. 2. The quality produced. In producing products, companies try to make these products have good quality. Because the resulting product is not right, employee productivity will decrease. 3. Error rate. One of the causes of reduced employee productivity in producing products is the error rate. Because the error rate is high, then productivity will be low. 4. Time required. Production process activities determine sufficient time. If the time given to produce the product is insufficient, it will make less so that the production target is not achieved.

So it can be concluded that work productivity is the relationship between the number of products produced (output) and (input) the amount of each resource needed with a more general formula, namely the ratio between satisfaction, needs, and sacrifices given and also as a mental attitude that always holds the view that quality life today must be better than yesterday and tomorrow better than today.

Research related to productivity, researched by several researchers, among others (Johari & Jha, 2020), concluded in their study that by increasing workers' motivation, their productivity and their likelihood of living and working in one particular location increased substantially. Other studies (Karimi & Asadnia, 2020) that motivation can trigger productivity. And with productivity will be able to create creativity at work (Hill, 2020).

Based on the study of work productivity theories, it can be synthesized that lecturer work productivity is the achievement of the results of all the potential of the lecturer by utilizing the resources they have concerning time, quantity, and quality in carrying out their duties to carry out the tri dharma of higher education.

DISCUSSION

This research's main objective is to prove the existence of a relationship between facets of motivation, attitude, and non-physical fatigue with work productivity in higher education. Many variables can influence non-physical fatigue. Fatigue at work is a subjective feeling accompanied by decreased efficiency and a need for work (Verawati, 2017).

Humans are the most vital resource in an organization. Human resources support the organization with their human resources, talents, and creative ideas. No matter how perfect the financial and technological resources they have, the organization will find it challenging to achieve its goals (Muayyad & Gawi, 2017). Human resource management is part of organizational leadership that focuses on the element of human resources. Its activities include planning, procurement, development, maintenance, and human resources to achieve goals both individually and in an organization. According to Sutrisno (2012), one of the goals of human resource management is to improve productivity levels, improve the quality of work-life, and convince the organization that it meets legal aspects.

Motivation is a concept expressed as a need (needs) and incentives (incentives), which cannot be separated because they are interrelated. Motivation is the cause of action, namely the conditions that initiate the behavior or activity. Robbins (2001) views motivation as a willingness to make a high effort towards organizational goals conditioned by meeting individual needs. Motivation is the result of interactions between individuals and the existing situation. Work motivation is directed to achieve goals where behind the behavior there is a kind of need, longing, and desire. The market implies shortcomings, and that deficiency may be satisfied if the objectives have been achieved. Willingness and desire imply a strong feeling.

Motivation itself in the existence of motivation is divided into two, namely intrinsic and extrinsic. Extrinsic motivation is motivation that arises due to external factors, for example, those related to economic factors (Siagian, 2003; Newcomb, 1989; Subandowo, 2009), such as salaries, honoraria, or other incentives such as the hope of getting promoted quickly, to get praise. And a good impression or vice versa to avoid reprimands and bad judgments from superiors.

Fatigue is a hazard in the workplace and can be linked to the safety and health of workers. It affects the health and safety of employees and associates. The term "fatigue" has wide usage in occupational medicine. Fatigue is a complex phenomenon that can be attributed to many factors. Therefore, it isn't easy to find a comprehensive definition with a universal agreement for it. Also, other terms like sleepiness and drowsiness are often used in the literature interchangeably instead of fatigue. One of them is the aspect of fatigue, and then it is easier to define it compared to fatigue. The first step in the approach to complaining of fatigue is to distinguish between sleepiness and fatigue. Distinguishing between them can be difficult even for specialists, but multiple sleep latency tests can help (Gander, Purnell, Garden, & Woodward, 2007).

Gibson (1997) describes attitudes as positive or negative feelings or mental states that are always prepared, studied, and regulated through experiences that have a remarkable effect on a person's response to people, objects, or situations. Attitude is more a determinant of behavior because attitudes are related to perception, personality, and motivation (Camiah, 1998). Employees will take and everything that employees must do, which results are proportional to the effort done. Work attitudes have a mental side that affects individuals in reacting to stimuli about themselves obtained from experience being able to respond to different stimuli. Some respond positively, and some respond negatively.

Productivity is an essential thing for a company organization, whether it is engaged in producing goods or services. In general, productivity is the ratio between output and input. The existence of adequate employee productivity will assist the company's efforts in developing the business. Increasing productivity so far has been mostly done through increasing knowledge and skills even though not only that but motivation is necessary to support employee work productivity (Lestari, 2019).

Productivity is a mental attitude that always tries to improve the quality of life sustainably through increasing efficiency, effectiveness, and quality (Siagian, 2018). When efficiency is a measure of the level of savings in the use of inputs in producing goods or services. Effectiveness is a measure of the level of target achievement of a process of creating goods or services, both in terms of quantity and quality (Regulation of the Minister of Manpower and Transmigration of the Republic of Indonesia Number PER.21 / MEN / IX / 2009 concerning Guidelines for Productivity Services). Thus, productivity is essential because productivity has a significant role in determining the success or failure of a business. Therefore, productivity must be an inseparable part of compiling a business strategy, including production, marketing, finance, and other fields (M. Subandowo, 2017).

The research results on the relationship between fatigue and productivity are in line with the study conducted (Umboh, Kawatu, & Ratag, 2020), which states that work fatigue is related to productivity. Fatigue can indeed reduce work performance and work productivity (Liengme et al., 2015). On the other hand, work fatigue can also have various consequences. As stated by Duhita Pangesti Putri (2008), Rosanti et al. (2014), Subandowo (2009) that there are two work fatigue, namely physical work fatigue and general work fatigue. Work fatigue is generally complained of as fatigue in attitudes, orientation, and workplace adjustments

experienced by workers who experience work fatigue (Setyowati, Shaluhayah, & Widjasena, 2014). This general fatigue is often referred to as psychic fatigue or nervous fatigue (ILO, 1986). Meanwhile, physical work fatigue occurs due to prolonged muscle contraction, which results in muscle processes and muscle fiber metabolism being unable to produce the same work output or the energy output in question decreases and their work productivity decreases.

CONCLUSION

From the studies and discussions that have been carried out above, it can be concluded that: (1) the motivation factor has a significant effect on job satisfaction. In general, employees will be motivated because of several factors. One of them is an exciting and challenging job, an atmosphere that gives trust (trust), making them personally responsible for the results and being involved in the organization's growth and development, (2) attitude is a statement or evaluative consideration regarding objects, people, or events, and work attitudes can affect lecturers' performance in higher education, (3) stressors can harm the body because a person's energy is limited and can run out at any time. If this happens, permanent damage to the body—non-physical fatigue results from work stress, work conflicts, the physical environment, and work capacity. There is a relationship between stress and non-physical fatigue, and (4) lecturer work productivity is the achievement of all the lecturer's potential by utilizing the resources they have concerning time, quantity, and quality in carrying out their duties to carry out higher education's tri dharma.

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